

STELUM: A Progress Report

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Abstract

We present a summary of our ongoing efforts on STELUM. A short name for tools for STELLar modeling from Université de Montréal. We aim to provide a package with applications for stellar modelization of static/equilibrium models, stellar evolution, pulsations along with utilities like graphic presentations or opacity table computations. Although that the various applications are highly configurable they are specialized for white dwarfs, subdwarfs, main sequence and horizontal branch stars with an emphasis on various mechanisms of particles transport. A description of the current applications is presented here along with some results. A roadmap of the future additions is also provided.

1 The package and some specificities

The source is written mainly in modern Fortran dialect (along with multi-processing) with an emphasis on highly modular units build with the Fortran 90 module feature. Some utilities and the applications launcher are written in Python 3. These applications was developed to fulfil our specific needs but also in the goal of a more general scope: mainly for an ease of use and to appeal to a larger base of users. Numerous options (actually 357!) are available and they can be set directly at run time without any recompilation. Models I/O file formats are fully customizable by the user and can be used by the various apps as long as a minimal subset of quantities are provided. Similarly, user can define generic stellar template providing the chemical species distribution along with the luminosity distribution. About 20% of the Fortran code is automatically generated from data and user supplied files.

2 The evol app

This is the main application of the package: the evolution code. This is not a full fledged code such as MESA (Paxton *et al.*, 2011) but a code with a more narrower and specialized scope: to study the various transport mechanism coupled with evolution. They are many departures from a “classical” evolution code. First, the produced models are complete models, i.e. models with the envelope and up into the atmosphere to $\log(\tau) \approx -5$. Second, phenoma with a typical lifetime much shorter than the evolutionary timescale (such as an accretion episode) can be precisely followed. Finally, the rate of change of all the chemical species are given by the following time-dependant equation:

$$\frac{dX_i}{dt} = \left(\frac{dX_i}{dt} \right)_{\text{src}} - \frac{1}{\rho r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left\{ \rho r^2 \left[(v_i + v_w) X_i + K \frac{\partial X_i}{\partial r} \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

This is an enhanced version of the usual diffusion equation. The first term is a local/external source term with contributions from nuclear reactions, accretions or winds. In the second term, v_i is the individual velocity of specie i (from gravitational settling, thermal diffusion and/or radiative levitation) while v_w is the wind velocity. Large scale motions from convection, over-shooting, semi-convection and ther-

mohaline mixing are given by the diffusion coefficient K . Transport equations are solved simultaneously for all the atomic species.

3 The model app

Another important application of the package: stellar modelization. This application can be used to build complete or envelope models. Complete models are available in thermal equilibrium or, for static ones, on a white dwarf cooling sequence. A first use of such models is for a starting model for an evolution run. Another important use is that, because they can be evaluated rapidly, they can be used in detailed seismic analysis.

Various templates are provided (such as DA, DB, SdB, ZAHB, Proto solar, etc...) and can be user-defined. Theses template are used to specify the composition run of the various chemical species and of the luminosity. Numerous options are available to closely match theses models with those found in fully evolutionary run.

4 The pulse app

This application is for everything related to stellar oscillations. From a given model we can evaluate adiabatic and non-adiabatic eigenperiods (or eigenfrequencies). Additional quantities such as work integral, rotation kernel, tide coupling parameters are also available.

5 Utilities apps

- `grmod`: plot of quantities extracted from models. Can show any quantities extracted from model files. In some cases, it can also show quantities evaluated from other ones in the model, say, for example $U = 4\pi\rho r^3/M_r$. Examples are provided by Fig. 2 and 4.
- `grseq`: more general plot extracted from an entire sequence. Examples are provided by Fig. 1 and 3.
- `table`: build-up of opacity tables. Sources are OP and OPAL. User can specify the composition/mixture
- `dump`: extract data from sequence for quick examination during runs
- `b2t`: translate a given model/sequence to a specified output file format

- make: not the usual makefile. Build parts of the Fortran code on the fly. Provide an analysis of the code to detect circular dependencies between the various modules

6 Roadmap

Beta (Currently)

- Some rough edges need to be polished.
- Completion of the semi-convective and the thermohaline diffusion modules.

1.0 (Beginning 2019)

- Computation of the “transport” flux fully consistent with the various transport mechanism (at this time, only the usual convective flux is available)
- Many “quality of life” improvements for the users

1.1 (Summer 2019)

- Rewriting of a old part in the model application
- Adding radiative forces module

1.2 (Late 2019)

- Multilingual version
- User manual

1.3 (Spring 2020)

- Python interface

2.0 (Late 2020)

- Website design
- Open-source version

7 Sample results: Modeling a SdB star from a low-mass ZAHB star progenitor

The starting model is $0.4842 M_{\odot}$, 37,000K ZAHB star. Model is composed of a pure He core ($Z=0.0!$) surrounded by a thin envelope of pure H of $1.6 \times 10^{-6} M_{\star}$. Figures 1 and 2 show the evolution of the star along the central He-burning phase. At the end, the resulting core has a mass of about $0.55 M_{\star}$ with a composition $X_C = 0.16$ and $X_O=0.84$.

8 Sample results: Spectral evolution of a PG-1159 stars

The starting model is a $0.6 M_{\odot}$, 106,000K PG-1159 star. Model is formed from a homogeneous core of Carbon ($X_C=0.4$) and Oxygen ($X_O=0.6$) surrounded by an homogeneous envelope of Helium ($X_{He}=0.5$), Carbon ($X_C=0.4$) and Oxygen ($X_O=0.1$) of $0.00316 M_{\star}$ [or $\log(1 - M_r/M_{\star}) = -2.5$]. Winds are given by the empirical law from Quirion *et al.* (2012).

From figures 3 and 4, we see that the star quickly becomes a DO star: at 74,300K, after 1.36 Myr, the surface composition is almost pure He ($X_{He}>0.999$). At around 30,000K the deepening of the convection zone (along with an highly effective under-shooting) begins to bring back Carbon toward the surface. The DB star start to transform in a hot DQ star! At near 8000K the mixing is almost complete and the star exhibit it initial surface composition.

References

Paxton, B., Bildsten, L., Dotter, A., Herwig, F., Lesaffre, P., *et al.* 2011, ApJS, 192, 3.
 Quirion, P.-O., Fontaine, G., & Brassard, P. 2012, ApJ, 755, 128.

Figure 1: Evolution of the core composition during the He central burning phase of a subdwarf star alongside with a mapping of the efficiency of large scale motions. Allowing for a lowly effective over-shooting, along with elements diffusion, gives rise, starting from about 25Myr, to a partial mixing zone that build-up from a mix of small convective and radiative zones. A signature of semi-convection, that contribute to the growing core. After 175Myr, 3 “breath pulses” arise that bring fresh He in the core. One can note, on the scale of the figure, that theses events seem to be a sudden episode that bring a discontinuity in the central composition. This is not the case. For the biggest event at 190Myr, about 22,176 models was needed to follow the growth from $X_{\text{He}}=0.014$ to $X_{\text{He}}=0.245$ on a period of 207,000 years.

Figure 2: The evolution of the C profile during the central He burning phase of a subdwarf star, starting from the ZAHB.

Figure 3: Evolution of the surface composition in a cooling sequence of a PG-1159 star alongside with a mapping of the efficiency of large scale motions. Deep red patches shows the convection zones while the lighter zones are related to less effective process such as over and under-shooting or semi-convection. At $\log(1 - M_r/M_*) = -12$, near $\tau = 100$, an artificial turbulence coefficient was set to homogenize the atmosphere and to speed-up the computations.

Figure 4: The evolution of the He profile during the cooling of a PG-1159 star.